

Current institutional approaches to sensitive research data management

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Introduction:

Institutions are under increasing pressure to implement comprehensive research data governance and consistent data management practices, particularly in instances involving sensitive research data. The [ARDC's Institutional Underpinnings](#) project 'Building a decoder ring for sensitive data' was initiated to provide an overview of institutional levers available for use when developing strategies, policies, protocols and other mechanisms for sensitive research data management across a range of classifications.

Acknowledging that the governance and management of sensitive research data involves a complex mix of ethical, regulatory and technical components as well as diverse institutional approaches and maturities, a landscape report (this document) was produced to establish a foundational understanding of current practices across the Australian University sector. The findings of this report were subsequently used to inform the guidance provided in "*Decoding Sensitive Data Management*"¹ (the sensitive data decoder) as well as determine the suitable audience(s) for the same.

The landscape report summarises the key observations and findings from a survey developed to explore diverse institutional approaches to four (4) core thematic areas determined to be essential for the development of an effective sensitive data management response (Table 1). These thematic areas were selected, and questions developed based on work done by the Steering Committee to compare key areas of assessment across common security standards including the International Security Organisation Standard (ISO/IEC 27001), National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) Cybersecurity Framework and the Australian Information Security Manual. The full questionnaire is included in Appendix 1. The participating institutions are listed in Table 2.

Table 1. Core thematic areas explored in the survey

Data Classification	Skills and Capabilities
Data Governance	Data Security

Table 2. Participating institutions

The University of Tasmania (UTAS)	The University of New South Wales (UNSW)	Central Queensland University (CQU)
The University of Melbourne (UoM)	Monash University (Monash)	Griffith University (Griffith)

¹Charlesworth J, Abdel Alim M, Brown D, Burton N, D'Costa K, Cho KL, Healey N, Lynn H, Morse J, Soo A-L, Splawa-Neyman P (2024) *Decoding Sensitive Data Management*. ARDC Ltd. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10403631>

Data Classification

Observation 1: There is significant nuance in how each institution has undertaken its implementation of a classification scheme and the assessment of what is captured in each classification tier.

Additionally, there is no clear and consistent definition of 'sensitive' data between institutional classification schemas and the actual distinction between the 'sensitive data' tiers of a classification (sensitive/highly sensitive or orange/red) is different across institutions.

To enable any recommendations or cross-institutional collaboration using sensitive research data, it is important for researchers to understand the sensitivity of the data they're working with, and for institutions to have some degree of consistency in how sensitive data is managed, protected and governed. As such, all the participating institutions were asked to provide their institutional data classification scheme. Those which are publicly available schema are listed below in Table 3.

Table 3. Publicly available data classification schema from participating institutions

- [UTAS - Data Classification Framework](#)
- [UNSW - Data Classification Standard](#)
- [Monash University - Security classifications for research data](#)
- [CQU - Information Assets Security Classification Policy](#)
- [Griffith University - Information Security Classification](#)

'Standard' Data Classification standards

Most institutions use **four categories**, however the two Queensland universities currently have five categories to align more closely with the [Protective Security Policy Framework \(PSPF\)](#) and [Queensland Government Information Security Classification Framework](#). Although CQU has noted an update in development which will result in a four-tiered system.

The definition of each classification tier did not appear to differ significantly between institutional policies or frameworks. All schema describe classification tiers dependant on the **risk presented to the institution** in relation to loss, misuse, or exposure of said data, with risks largely noted as being legislatively driven e.g., impact of breaching the Privacy Act. Monash, Griffith and CQU, also assess risk based on data **availability and integrity**. Notably, the streamlined guidance provided to researchers does not tend to include these additional dimensions.

The survey also sought to understand if classification standards between enterprise and research data varied at an institution. Except for UoM, all institutions identified that a single classification policy encompassed both enterprise and research data with interpretations for each type of data contained within the policy itself or supporting documentation. The pros

and cons of this approach are extensively discussed in the [earlier Institutional Underpinnings project relating to data classification](#) and will not be reiterated here.

Defining ‘sensitive’ data

A significant difference between the institutional classification schemas compared is the nomenclature used to describe the categories, particularly for the top two tiers of data sensitivity e.g., sensitive vs very/highly sensitive, protected vs critical, or sensitive vs confidential. The concerns around the impact of these naming conventions and potential for confusion can be found in our [earlier Institutional Underpinnings report](#). Notably, both UoM and UTAS have adopted the traffic light style system where categories of sensitivity are assigned a corresponding colour (i.e., orange and red).

Regardless of naming conventions, the nuance of the distinction between orange and red or sensitive and highly sensitive is quite variable and doesn’t easily facilitate direct mapping between institutions’ categories. There appears to be variability in the agreement of the research data types which constitute the highest risk for an institution and should therefore be assigned the highest sensitivity. Key examples include data involving children, personally identifiable information and health or medical data which have been differentially categorised by participating institutions. While this is likely a result of the varying risk appetite of institutions, it warrants further consideration to determine whether there can be some degree of national consistency regarding the definition of ‘sensitive research data’. While the ideal scenario would then be to mandate all institutions to use the same data classification framework, we acknowledge that this is unlikely to occur without some major Federal-level intervention.

Case study 1 – Classifying sensitive data: UTAS

The [UTAS Data Classification Framework](#), utilises the Green to Red nomenclature (Figure 1)

Figure 1. UTAS Data Classification Scheme

Within this classification, both Orange and Red categories represent variants of sensitive data, and the distinction between the categories is based on risk/consequence where breach or misuse ‘may have a major adverse impact’ vs ‘expected to cause severe harm’ to the University or an external party. However, when assessing the details that separate these two categories (Figure 2) it becomes apparent that Orange is by far the largest category, containing the bulk of research data (including re-identifiable data, data with cultural or ecological sensitivity, personally identifiable information and data subject to contractual

restrictions). The Red tier covers a much smaller subset of data with much more extreme risk associated (i.e., ‘significant ethical implications or commercial value’).

<p>Red</p> <p>Data breach or misuse expected to cause severe harm to the university or an external party. Release could be a regulatory or criminal offence.</p>	
<p>Information where unauthorised access, alteration, loss, misuse, or disclosure may have a major adverse impact on the University, another organisation or individual(s).</p> <p>The information has a restricted audience, and access must only be authorised based on strict academic, research or business need.</p> <p>Compromise may constitute a breach of legal or regulatory responsibilities.</p> <p><i>Disclosure to third parties is for specific purposes and requires authorisation.</i></p> <p>Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Personally identifiable data as defined by the Privacy Act ● Re-identifiable sensitive data ● Culturally, ecologically or commercially sensitive data ● Data with ‘commercial in confidence’ or other contractual restrictions 	<p>Information where unauthorised access, alteration, loss, misuse, or disclosure could reasonably be expected to seriously and adversely impact the University, another organisation or individual(s).</p> <p>The information has a restricted audience, and access may be subject to regulatory obligations.</p> <p>Compromise would constitute a breach of legal or regulatory responsibilities.</p> <p><i>Disclosure to third parties is for specific purposes and requires authorisation.</i></p> <p>Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data with extreme commercial or strategic sensitivity including trade secrets ● Unpublished research with significant ethical implications or commercial potential

Figure 2. The distinction between Orange and Red in the UTAS Data Classification Scheme

As an example, a researcher working on a medical research project collecting personally identifiable data or health records for identifiable participants would generally have their data classified as Orange, the same as a researcher working on recording the location of threatened species or someone working on reconstructing lost languages.

The Red category only applies once these data develop some degree or critical mass of additional sensitivity that would result in an *expected serious adverse impact if breached or misused*. For instance, if an entire species could be lost due to releasing its physical location, or if a medical research study were collecting detailed mental health and religious belief information for a large and identifiable cohort of minors.

The difference between this UTAS exemplar and some of the other classification frameworks we compared in this project relates primarily to the handling of personally identifiable data. Some classification schemes categorised data not only due to its inherent characteristics but also due to the inclusion in specific legislation as a means of assessing classification beyond impacts of breach or misuse e.g., assigning increased sensitivity to certain data types because of their definition in the Australian Privacy Act. This case study does, however, support the idea that a spectrum of controls and governance mechanisms that can be applied to support sensitive data management would potentially have more utility than a purely categorical approach of classifying data into Orange vs Red.

Guidance to researchers

All institutions identified a baseline level of guidance to their researchers which involved documentation either in the classification policy itself or contained separately e.g. as a separate procedure/guideline document or webpage. UoM and Monash were currently the only institutions to publish a tool which would help researchers classify their data by responding to a series of questions ([UoM Research Data Classification Tool](#), Monash' ['How Sensitive Is Your Research Data?'](#) Tool). Institutions also identified that checkpoints through the research process such as data management planning, ethics applications, and data storage requests often involved classification steps with appropriate guidance. Other resources that have been identified include online tools also published at UoM and Monash that help researchers identify which institutional systems are appropriate for use once a classification has been applied to their data.

Data Governance

Observation 2: The distributed nature of the way research is conducted; research data is generated and the way that it is managed in an institutional system presents complex challenges for the governance of sensitive research data.

Carving out research data decision-making processes from both broader institutional data and from the infrastructures (predominantly digital) within which the data sits is very much institutionally dependent. Commonality between institutions in data governance largely lies in the challenge of enabling holistic oversight over distributed and researcher reliant processes.

Data governance is the cross-functional framework for handling data that specifies decision making rights and responsibilities, formalises data policies, standards and procedures and monitors compliance.² Effectively, these are the rules that govern how data activities are undertaken. Implementing effective research data governance is complex for most organisations as most decisions regarding research data are made by individual researchers, rather than at the university-organisation level.³ This distributed nature of the decision-making (and in many cases the actual research data) poses particular challenges when 'sensitive research data' is involved.

Data governance mechanisms are often described around the concepts of the four Ps (People, Policy, Processes, Products/ tools) (Figure 3).

² Abraham, Rene, Schneider, Johannes, & vom Brocke, Jan. (2019). Data governance: A conceptual framework, structured review, and research agenda. *International Journal of Information Management*, 49, 424–438. <https://doi.org/10.101>

³ ARC/NHMRC The Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research (2018)

Figure 3: Overview of common data governance mechanisms

The participating institutions were surveyed specifically around these governance mechanisms:

- **People:** To identify the decision makers at the institution involved in research data governance
- **Policy:** To identify the policies and procedures related to ‘sensitive research data’
- **Process:** To understand their ability to identify people and projects using ‘sensitive research data’ and monitor to the handling of ‘sensitive research data’
- **Products:** To capture the guidance provided on how ‘sensitive research data’ should be managed using appropriate technology and management practices

People - Who are the institutional decision-makers involved in Research Data Governance?

Institutional decision-making around research data varied across respondents with only one institution clearly defining a “Data Champion” in the digital research domain (UTAS) who reported to both the DVCR and the Chief Information Officer. It is common across all institutions to have a high level, university-wide governance group responsible for the strategic direction of ‘sensitive data management’ e.g., to review policies. However, as governance becomes more granular, diversification into the approach used is observed. Figure 4 summarises the diversity in existing governance structures reported.

It was also noted by institutions that working groups or advisory committees have been established in the past to support specific governance purposes. Furthermore, smaller areas or units within the institution (such as in particular schools or departments) may have

additional local governance committees for their identified sensitive data management requirements. This level of implementation has not been included in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Institutional Decision Making in Research Data Governance

Policy - Which institutional policies relate to 'sensitive' research data?

Similar to the roles and responsibilities associated with research data governance, the surveyed institutions also reported having various policies that either applied to all data in the institution (e.g., a Cybersecurity or Information security Policy) or specifically to just research data (e.g., a Research Data Management Policy). A summary of the policies relating to 'sensitive' data can be found at Table 4.

In Table 4, the following descriptions apply:

The governance document explicitly distinguishes between research and enterprise data or there are separate documents for enterprise and research data.

The governance document is only relevant to research data.

The governance document does not explicitly reference research data however, the scope of the document may still extend to research data.

Please note, this table does not include a comprehensive review of all governance policies or documents applicable in the participating institution. It only compares a small subset of policies deemed to be relevant to sensitive research data management and identified by respondents in the survey. There may be other governance documents not compared in this table.

Data Governance					Policy	Policy
Data Management	Policy & Procedure		Policy	Policy & Procedure	(data handling) Policy and Guideline	Procedure
Cybersecurity/ Information Security	Policy		Policy	Policy	Policy and Standards	Procedure
ICT Use	Procedure		Policy	Policy and Procedure	Policy	Procedure
Data Breach			Procedure		Policy and procedure	Procedure
Data Classification	Policy		Framework	Procedure	Standard	Standard
Integrity, Misconduct and Ethics	Policy		Policy	Procedure	Procedure	Policy & Procedure
Privacy	Policy		Policy	Procedure	Policy	Policy & Statement

Table 4: Policies and procedures at each institution applicable to 'sensitive research data'

Process – Does the institution have the ability to identify ‘sensitive research data’ and monitor the ways it is used or handled?

Given the complexity, variety, volume and distributed nature of responsibility for research data, it is not surprising that an automated identification of ‘sensitive research data’ is not currently possible. All institutions identified that they rely on researchers to categorise their data, however there are multiple common engagement checkpoints that facilitate or mandate this process being completed by researchers. Table 5 summarises the checkpoints requiring researchers to identify the classification of their data.

While researchers may identify their data to be sensitive at any of these touchpoints, a common challenge across institutions is the ability to maintain holistic oversight once a research project is known to have sensitive data. For example, an ethics committee may first become aware of a research project involving sensitive data, however, this information is not disclosed to infrastructure teams unless provided by the researcher at the resource request stage. None of the participating institutions have currently established a central repository of sensitive research data collections.

This also prohibits the institutions’ ability to monitor or audit sensitive research data management practices for compliance with established policies and guidance. Institutions however, identified that this may be done for a specific process, e.g., the ethics process may require an audit for their approvals or at a local level with faculties, schools or departments have individual mechanisms of monitoring.

For Table 5, the following descriptions apply:

The process has an identification step for sensitive research data projects and all institutional research projects will engage in this process.

The process has an identification step for sensitive research data projects but may not capture sensitive research data projects that do not engage in this process.

A process is being established to include an identification step for sensitive research data projects.

Identified through:

	CQ University Australia	Griffith University	The University of Melbourne	Monash University	UNSW Sydney	University of Tasmania
Ethics Processes	●	◐	○	◐	◐	◐
Data Management Plan	●				◐	◐
Infrastructure Provision			◐	◐	◐	◐
Faculty/ School/ Institute/ Department			◐	◐	◐	◐

Table 5: Mechanisms or checkpoints for identifying 'sensitive research data'

'Product/Tools- What guidance is provided regarding the management of 'sensitive data'?

All participating institutions reported the publication of some level of guidance via static web pages (maintained by the library, IT, Digital or eResearch). Additionally, some institutions also provide the research community with opportunities to engage in personal consultations. The resources available to researchers are closely related, if not the same to those described in the 'Guidance to researchers' section above on Page 6.

Skills and Capabilities

Observation 3: There is very limited centrally managed training that is dedicated to sensitive data management. Reliance on other university wide training (which are largely mandatory) is the predominant mechanism for upskilling researchers on sensitive data management principles.

This section of the questionnaire assessed the strategies employed by participating universities to support the implementation of good 'sensitive data' management practices and uplift skills of researchers who utilise or manage sensitive research data. It has been acknowledged in the previous and current Institutional Underpinnings project phases that training is an integral part of supporting adherence to university policies and good research practice, however, this questionnaire has identified similar levels of maturity in training across all the participating universities.

It is also worth noting that the initiatives for uplifting the skills and capabilities of researchers in research data management is largely occurring at the university-wide scale, however UoM and UNSW have identified graduate research student specific research data management training exists (not mandatory at UoM and mandatory at UNSW).

Sensitive data specific Training Content

Dedicated sensitive research data management training courses appear to only exist at UNSW and Griffith University. Both of these however are not mandatory and are self-nominated by researchers. As discussed in previous sections of this report, all participating universities identified the existence of supporting resources or guidance as the predominant support and awareness mechanism for researchers handling sensitive data.

Training implementation and assessment

It was unanimously reported across the six universities that there was no mandatory sensitive data management training that extended across all research staff. A majority of universities surveyed identified that mandatory training courses such as *Cyber Security* training and *Research Integrity* training may provide context for sensitive research data management but do not directly address sensitive data management principles, concepts or practices.

As mandatory training related to sensitive data currently does not exist, assessing the effectiveness of training is currently not possible from the data collected. It was noted that evaluation of training programs is currently collected ad hoc in the form of feedback surveys. A standardised method of assessing the effectiveness of sensitive research data management training was not identified through the questionnaire.

It's important to note that the above findings refer to centrally managed training and that specialised training for specific types of sensitive research data (e.g., medical data) are handled by individual faculties or schools.

Data Security

Observation 4: Most universities report alignment of research systems to industry cyber security standards, occasionally including formal accreditations such as ISO27001 for research technology/capabilities of varying scope. As expected, there is significant variation across institutions regarding the processes to assess specific controls required for different classification categories.

Partner institutions were asked to report on how they addressed the technical/system-based aspects of data security, specifically on their approach to:

- The assessment of technology or systems for sensitive data management
- Setting and adhering to platform specific or baseline controls for data security
- If researchers are required to adhere to certain baseline controls for data security
- Formal standards/certifications around sensitive data systems
- Alignment of standards for enterprise and research systems

Table 6 below summarises responses as a comparison between institutions.

All partner institutions reported that security assessments were routinely undertaken for the procurement of new technologies or systems. These assessments were predominantly overseen by cybersecurity teams embedded within IT departments, with the involvement of other key areas, e.g., the Digital Research team at UTAS, the Research Data Management team at UoM, and/or formal oversight bodies e.g. the Solution Architecture Board at Griffith Architecture Review Board at UoM, dependent on the institution.

Each institutions' assessment processes were different (with an example from UoM represented below) with varying levels of standardisation and maturity. However, a few universities mentioned utilising a risk-based approach in these processes. Griffith, UNSW and UTAS reported that systems with higher identified risk, either due to the type of data hosted on the system and/or the context of the system, were then targeted for additional analyses/assessments and the implementation of specific controls. At UoM, the same assessment process was applied to all systems, but the nature of the data or the context of the system influences the depth of the assessment and determines whether additional activities, such as penetration testing, are necessary.

While most responses did not detail the specifics of the controls examined, some examples provided included data storage in Australia and features such as multi-factor authentication and encryption. Responses highlighted that controls are aligned to industry best practice standards such as the NIST Cybersecurity Framework, ISO/IEC 27001 for Information Security Management Systems and the Australian Cyber Security Centre Essential Eight.

These controls did not necessarily map against institutions' respective classification levels [see Data Classification section] in clear, definitive ways i.e. systems of each classification requiring a fixed set of controls. This may be due to a defence-in-depth methodology where

multiple measures and controls are layered to ensure data security and may also relate to an earlier discussion around the risk appetite of institutions. As such, the appropriateness of a technology or system for sensitive data is not necessarily determined by the presence or absence of a specific control, but rather the combination and particular configuration of controls.

Most partner institutions had achieved formal certifications or external assessments of their data security for particular systems/environments/projects within their institutions with the most commonly mentioned being Defence Industry Security Program (DISP) membership, followed by ISO27001 certification.

Entity responsible for assessment and/or sign off	Cybersecurity, Data Security Control Board	Cybersecurity, Solution Architecture Board	Cybersecurity, Information Security Council, RDM team	Cybersecurity	Cybersecurity	Cybersecurity, Digital Research team
Maturity of assessment process	?	Mature, with established governance oversight	Developing, requires embedding in BAU activities	?	Mature	Developing, requires embedding in BAU for research
Connection between assessment and classification framework	?	Yes	Yes	?	Yes	Yes
Alignment of standards used for enterprise and research	Mostly aligned, responsive to different reqs in the two domains	Aligned	Some alignment, responsive to different reqs in the two domains	Aligned	Mostly aligned, some distinction between risk profiles in the two domains	Some alignment, responsive to different reqs in the two domains
Formal accreditations achieved ⁴	QGISCF DISP Entry Level	None	ISO 27001 IRAP DISP Entry Level	ISO 27001 DISP Entry level	IRAP (interim) DISP Entry Level NSW eHealth PSAF	DISP Level 1

Table 6: Summary of key features of data security assessment process

⁴Institutions noted that these formal accreditations were achieved for certain projects or technologies/systems, rather than the University holistically.

Case study 2: UoM Approach to Assessment of Research Data Systems

Prior to the development of the University's Research Data Classification Framework in 2021-2022, the assessment of centrally provided research systems was a component of enterprise solution design and procurement processes, without nuance of the varying degrees of research data sensitivity and scaling security controls.

Driven by a need to provide researchers with actionable guidance for how to implement the newly published Research Data Classification Framework, UoM undertook a formal assessment process to benchmark the security posture of our commonly used research data storage and management systems against the four classifications in our developed framework (Green, Yellow, Orange, Red). 20 systems were identified for the initial evaluation.

In collaboration with the Cybersecurity team, the University's RDM Program team engaged with the respective system administrators to do a paper-based risk assessment of all in-scope systems.

Preliminary assessment involved mapping alignment of the systems to a series of baseline security controls, which were developed from a combination of an existing UoM Security Controls Library (for enterprise systems) and the following relevant industry best practice standards:

- The Australian Government Information Security Manual (ISM)
- International Security Organisation Standard - ISO 27001
- NIST 800-53
- NIST 800-63

The baseline security controls included, but were not limited to:

- Data storage in Australia
- Provision for backups
- Event logging
- Centralised access management/role-based access control
- Multi Factor authentication
- Data encryption
- Regular security testing
- Patch management
- Endpoint protection
- Network segmentation

Depending on the risk assessments of each system and configuration of the above controls, a classification level was assigned to each system, which indicated that data up to that classification was appropriate to be stored and/or managed on that system. This was conducted as a point-in-time assessment, with extension and standardisation of the assessment process for additional systems that have or will come online currently underway.

Final Observations and Conclusions

When the ARDC Institutional Underpinnings ‘Building a decoder ring for sensitive data’ project was established, participating institutions agreed there was a need to understand the alignment between institutional approaches to managing sensitive data. This was both to share knowledge between institutions seeking to mature their sensitive data capabilities, but also as an acknowledgment of the collaborative nature of research meaning researchers would be working across institutional processes.

While it was expected that direct comparison or standardisation across institutions would be difficult, this landscape summary was undertaken to establish a baseline understanding of common mechanisms used by institutions in managing their sensitive data.

The findings from the survey show that the overarching levers of an institution's sensitive data management strategy are largely the same. Variations between institutions mostly occur at the more granular levels of implementation, with some differences being more significant than expected, for example, how data is classified into the two highest classification tiers. Despite these variations, there is commonality in the challenges faced by each institution as noted throughout this report.

The aim of this landscape scan was not to identify which implementations were best, but to inform the framework for the ‘sensitive data decoder’⁵ (the second output of this project). It highlights that the decoder must be flexible for a range of possible implementations to be broadly useful, as institutions will need to consider their specific context e.g., risk appetite, scale etc. to determine the suitability of any interventions.

Training and Awareness

Training and awareness raising activities arose as the most significant area for improvement across all institutions. There was no consensus on whether all researchers require some form of sensitive data training or only those with identified sensitive data projects. To enable the second option, a common challenge would be ensuring the underlying infrastructure and metadata collection could enable the identification of researchers for targeted training.

Another key challenge was the distributed nature of research data management support activities. In most cases, support for research data occurs in areas such as IT, central Research Offices, eResearch, Library, Records and Archives, with each area providing a different perspective on support and training. Defining clear responsibilities for research

⁵Charlesworth J, Abdel Alim M, Brown D, Burton N, D’Costa K, Cho KL, Healey N, Lynn H, Morse J, Soo A-L, Splawa-Neyman P (2024) Decoding Sensitive Data Management. ARDC Ltd. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10403631>

data activities between these areas has the ability to enable enhancements to research data support and training activities.

Raising researcher awareness of sensitive data support resources was also identified as a difficult issue to tackle. In particular, there was consensus that central communication channels are ineffective for reaching researchers. Many institutions highlighted those local areas (faculty/school/departments) often established more effective communication channels for their researchers. There is therefore a need to engage and collaborate more closely with local area representatives when developing communication strategies to effect culture change regarding the management of sensitive data.

Ownership and Resourcing of Research Data Policy and Governance

At many institutions, research data governance is distributed across a number of different business areas, with clear variations in the complexity and breadth of engagement across these business areas. There was commonality only in the highest level of governance at an institution wide level.

How the different governance structures reflect the context of each institution and any challenges and benefits the different structures provide was beyond the scope of the survey. Understanding this more granularly could provide considerable benefits in making recommendations for institutional change around sensitive data management. As such, the 'sensitive data decoder' recommendations must recognise the distributed nature of decision making associated with sensitive research data management and the fact that implementations can require multiple areas of an institution to be involved.

Complexity of Research

The diversity of research practice and complexity of research data involved presents challenges for all institutions, where a singular solution or approach will never suit all research requirements. The disconnect between enterprise data and research data was raised as an area of particular difficulty for a number of institutions. With data governance in most institutions designed for relatively less complex enterprise data, there was often difficulty applying the structures and processes in place to the research context. Assessing and expanding data governance processes to ensure appropriateness for research data is critical for effective sensitive data management.

Project Metadata

Improvement in institutional processes for collection of metadata for research data was highlighted by a number of institutions as an area of concern. There is a desire among some

institutions to implement research project registries or research information asset registers. Even for those institutions that have good metadata processes in place, having compliance or review processes for this data is ad hoc and could be improved if linked more effectively to active governance processes.

Mandatory Processes

The last area of difficulty across many institutions was the ability to achieve support for implementation of mandatory processes concerning researcher training, collection of project metadata, or use of endorsed platforms. This is exacerbated by distributed responsibility for data governance, limited understanding of sensitive research data best practice and limited awareness of suitable platforms. Without high-level leadership advocacy for improving sensitive research data management processes, change in this space will remain slow.

Appendix 1. Discovery of project partners' current state: Institutional approach to sensitive data management questionnaire

Data Classification:

- Does your institution have a Data Classification framework?
 - If yes, is it the same scheme for research data and university operating/enterprise data?
 - Please provide details of and how the framework is used, governed etc.
 - Can you link or attach the summary?
- What criteria does your institution use to determine the sensitivity and confidentiality levels of research data? (i.e. if you have a data classification, what determines the difference between the top two categories?)
- Does your institution provide specific guidelines for researchers to classify and handle sensitive data?
- What is the uptake of your classification framework amongst the research community and how has this been or how will this be achieved?

Data Governance:

- Does your institution have mechanisms for identifying researchers or research projects with sensitive research data?
- What governance mechanisms (e.g. committees, review, or audit processes) does your institution have in place to ensure sensitive data is being appropriately managed?
- Who contributes to institutional decision making around research data management and governance at your university and how? Please include the main key parties e.g. working group made up of X meeting monthly, CIO makes all the decisions, data stewardship team responsible for rolling out user-facing support etc.
- Are your researchers provided with specific guidance on sensitive research data management? e.g., around storing, sharing or desensitisation. If yes, please provide some details.
- Describe (in brief) the primary policies, guidelines, and governance instruments you have in place for research data management and governance? Are these specific to research data or do they relate to all data?

Skills and Capabilities:

- How do you ensure that all researchers and staff involved in handling sensitive data are adequately trained and aware of their responsibilities?
- What training programs or resources does your institution provide to researchers and staff for effective sensitive research data management? Are any of these mandatory?
- How do you assess the effectiveness of your data management training programs and identify areas for improvement?

Data Security:

- What is your institution's approach to the assessment of technology or systems for sensitive data management?
- Does your institution have separate Enterprise cyber security controls/standards and Research cyber security controls/standards and who has the authority for primary decision making in these areas? Please provide details.
- Has your institution implemented a formal standard for sensitive data in any research context such as DISP, ISO27001, NIST standards etc.
 - If yes, please provide summary details (when, which standard, what)
 - If No, what is your (estimated) institutional maturity on the security protections required for different levels of research data sensitivity? i.e., mature, in progress, we have a plan, non-existent.
 - Is your institution planning to implement a formal standard for sensitive data in any research context within the next 12 months?
- Are there any platform-specific or baseline controls for data security that you follow or require researchers to adhere to?

General questions for reflection:

- Of the areas discussed above, what do you feel has the biggest opportunity for improvement and why?
- Of the areas discussed above, what is or has been the most difficult area for your institution to adequately address and why?